

Electroanalysis of Chloramphenicol Palmitate Dosage Forms

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The electrochemical reduction behaviour of chloramphenicol palmitate has been studied by employing advanced electrochemical techniques in different pH values. Based on the kinetic parameters evaluated, electrode mechanism is proposed. DPP method has been developed for its determination in different pharmaceutical dosage forms using the method of standard addition.

Chloramphenicol palmitate (1) is of choice for the treatment of typhoid and paratyphoid fevers, but it does not eliminate the typhoid carrier state. It is also used in the treatment of Haemophilus influenzae meningitis and rickettsial infections¹. Chloramphenicol is an extremely valuable antibiotic and titrimetric², spectrophotometric³ and chromatographic procedures⁴ have been outlined for its determination in pharmaceuticals and biological materials. Salvensen⁵ reported the analytical control of chloramphenicol and chloramphenicol palmitate by nonaqueous titration. A survey of the literature reveals that no attempt has been made yet to study the electrochemical behaviour of chloramphenicol palmitate. Hence, we undertook the title investigation using electrochemical techniques such as D.C. polarography, cyclic voltammetry, A.C. polarography, differential pulse polarography, rotating ring disk voltammetry, millicoulometry and controlled potential electrolysis. Also, an attempt has been made to determine quantitatively the title compound in pharmaceutical formulations by using differential pulse polarography without any prior separation.

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Results and Discussion

Chloramphenicol palmitate is found to be reduced in a single well defined wave/peak in all the buffer systems studied over the entire pH range (2.0–12.0). Typical voltammograms are given in Figs. 1–3. This wave/peak corresponds to four-electron reduction of a nitro group to a hydroxylamine group. A small anodic peak (a_1 at -0.16 V vs Ag/AgCl(s) Cl⁻) also has been observed in the reverse scan of the cyclic voltammogram at the

higher pH range ($\text{pH} \geq 10.0$) as shown in Fig. 2. It is quite likely that nitroso compound is formed, whose moment at electrode surface may be responsible for the anodic peak. In the second scan, another cathodic peak is obtained which may be due to the reduction of nitroso compound formed at a_1 to hydroxylamine⁶.

where R is chloramphenicol palmitate moiety excluding the NO_2 group.

In D.C. polarography, a maximum is noticed for the reduction of nitro group in all the supporting electrolytes employed. This maximum is easily suppressed in the presence of Triton X-100 (0.002%).

The diffusion-controlled and adsorption-free nature of the reduction process is evidenced from the linear plots of i_d vs $h^{1/2}$, i_p vs $v^{1/2}$, i_m vs $t^{2/3}$ and I_{1d} vs $w^{1/2}$ passing through origin. The current function $i_p/Cv^{1/2}$ is found to be fairly constant with respect to scan rate (v) indicating the electrode process to be free from any kinetic complications. The collection efficiency ($N=0.176$) calculated from rotating ring disk voltammetry is found to be in good agreement with the theoretical value (0.179) also indicating the absence of kinetic complications. The electrochemical reduction process is found to be irreversible as evidenced from the variation of reduction potentials with concentration of the depolariser, log-plot analysis, disobedience of Tomes' criterion and absence of anodic peak in the reverse scan and the variation of peak potential with the scan rate in cyclic voltammetry. The marginal variation of peak potential (E_m) with concentration and non-linearity in the plots of i_m vs $(1-\varphi)/(1+\varphi)$ in differential pulse polarography also confirm the irreversible nature of the electrode process.

Millicoulometric technique has been employed for the determination of the number of electrons (n) involved in the electrode process and n is found to be four in different pH zones evaluated. Controlled

potential electrolysis also agrees with the above results. Controlled potential electrolysis was carried out in pH 2.0 at -0.17 V vs SCE, and the product is identified as hydroxylamine which is confirmed by ir spectral studies ($\nu_{\text{jol}}; 3300$ and 3050 cm^{-1}).

The various kinetic parameters such as diffusion coefficient (D) and heterogeneous forward rate constant ($K_{f,h}^0$) values evaluated from the different techniques are furnished in Table 1. The diffusion coefficient values evaluated from different techniques are observed to be in good agreement. This is evident particularly since no adsorption complications are involved. The heterogeneous forward rate constant values are found to be high in acidic media in all the techniques since in this media high proton involvement makes the nitro group protonated which in turn gets reduced more easily. But in basic media, the reduction of nitro group is not easily facilitated owing to the less-availability of protons⁷. The $E_{1/2}$ vs pH plot indicates the number of protons involved in the rate determining step to be one⁸.

Analysis: In the present investigation, the experimental data of differential pulse polarography are used to work analytical procedures for the estimation of title compound in pure form and in dosage forms. The peak obtained in the pH zones $2.0 \leq \text{pH} \leq 6.0$ is well-resolved and may be utilised for the analysis by employing both calibration and standard addition methods. Using the calibration method, the peak height is found to be linear over the concentration range 1.0×10^{-5} to $2.2 \times 10^{-7} M$ and the lower detection limit is found to be $1.95 \times 10^{-7} M$.

Recommended analytical procedure: Standard solution ($1.0 \times 10^{-5} M$) is prepared by dissolving the appropriate amount of drug in DMF. pH 4.0 is found to be a suitable medium for the analysis of the drug. The unknown solution (1 ml) is transferred into a cell and made up with the supporting electrolyte (9 ml) and then deaerated with oxygen-free nitrogen gas for 10 min. After recording the polarogram, small increments (0.2 ml) of standard solution are added and polarograms

TABLE 1—TYPICAL ELECTROCHEMICAL DATA FOR CHLORAMPHENICOL PALMITATE
Concn. = 0.5 mM

Supporting electrolyte of pH	D. C. polarography (Drop time: 3 s)			Cyclic voltammetry (Scan rate: 60 mV s ⁻¹)			A. C. polarography (Drop time: 3 s)			Differential pulse polarography (drop time: 2 s)			Rotating disk voltammetry (Sweep rate: 50 mV s ⁻¹)	
	$-E_{1/2}$ V	$D \times 10^6 \text{ cm}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$	$k_{f,h}^0 \text{ cm s}^{-1}$	$-E_p$ V	$D \times 10^6 \text{ cm}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$	$-k_{f,h}^0 \text{ cm s}^{-1}$	$E_s D \times 10^6 \text{ V cm}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$	$k_s \text{ cm s}^{-1}$	$-E_m$ V	$D \times 10^6 \text{ cm}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$	$k_{f,h}^0 \text{ cm s}^{-1}$	$D \times 10^6 \text{ cm}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$	$k_{f,h}^0 \text{ cm s}^{-1}$	
2.0	0.15	2.21	9.24×10^{-4}	0.13	2.42	9.32×10^{-4}	0.16	2.19×10^{-3}	0.11	2.52	6.81×10^{-4}	3.12	9.82×10^{-4}	
4.0	0.24	2.15	3.83×10^{-5}	0.23	2.34	8.64×10^{-5}	0.27	2.35×10^{-4}	0.26	2.05	5.52×10^{-5}	3.08	1.12×10^{-5}	
6.0	0.39	2.08	1.32×10^{-6}	0.37	2.16	1.34×10^{-6}	0.40	1.96×10^{-5}	0.36	2.16	1.84×10^{-6}	3.01	9.48×10^{-6}	
8.0	0.45	2.01	8.54×10^{-7}	0.40	2.05	9.56×10^{-7}	0.48	1.85×10^{-5}	0.43	2.01	9.62×10^{-7}	2.94	4.62×10^{-6}	
10.0	0.55	1.96	4.62×10^{-7}	0.47	1.98	3.92×10^{-7}	0.56	1.82×10^{-5}	0.52	1.90	1.14×10^{-7}	2.92	1.82×10^{-7}	
12.0	0.57	1.91	5.72×10^{-8}	0.55	1.93	1.22×10^{-8}	0.59	1.74×10^{-6}	0.55	1.81	8.33×10^{-8}	2.88	6.70×10^{-8}	

Based on the results obtained from different techniques, the electrochemical reduction behaviour of chloramphenicol palmitate may be proposed as shown in Scheme 1.

recorded after each addition under similar conditions. The best precision is found to be obtained with a drop time of 2 s and a pulse amplitude of 50 mV (peak potential -0.26 V vs Ag/AgCl(s) Cl⁻). The standard deviation and correlation coefficient (for 10 replicants) are found to be 1.72% and 0.968 respectively.

Chloramphenicol palmitate in pharmaceutical preparations: The above described procedure is successfully employed for the determination of chloramphenicol palmitate in its dosage forms without any prior separation. Two chloramphenicol palmitate formulations, capsule and oral suspension are obtained from the manufacturer and assay results of the various dosage forms investigated are given in Table 2.

Comparison of the values obtained by the spectrophotometric method described in the British Pharmaceutical Codex for pure drug show that the results obtained for the pure drug by both the methods are in close agreement. Further, the recoveries, which are in the range 99.3–99.8%, in-

TABLE 2—ASSAY OF CHLORAMPHENICOL PALMITATE DOSAGE FORMS BY DIFFERENTIAL PULSE POLAROGRAPHY

Pulse amplitude=50 mV, drop time=2 s

Sample	Labelled amount mg	Amount found mg	Recovery %	Standard deviation
Chloramphen. palm. (Oral suspension)	75 (100 ml)	74.90	99.7	0.017
Chloramphen. palm. (Oral suspension)	50 (75 ml)	49.20	99.3	0.021
Chloromycetin palmitate (Capsule)	25	24.90	49.8	0.016

indicate the high accuracy and reproducibility of the proposed method.

Fig. 1. Typical d.c. polarogram of chloramphenicol palmitate in pH 2.0; concn.=0.5 mM, drop time=3 s.

Experimental

Pharmaceutical grade chloramphenicol palmitate supplied (Sigma) was used as such. The chemicals used were of A.R. grade. Polarographic experiments were performed using a PARC 364 polarographic analyser coupled with BD 8 Kipp-Zonen $x-t$ recorder. A dropping mercury electrode (flow rate, 2.73 mg s^{-1}) was used as the working electrode and a saturated calomel electrode (SCE) as the reference. A.C. and differential pulse polarograms were recorded with Metrohm unit coupled with E 506 Polarecord and E 612 VA scanner. Cyclic voltammograms were obtained by digital electronics 2000 $x-y/t$ recorder in conjunction with the above unit. A hanging mercury drop electrode of area 0.04439 cm^2 and dropping mercury electrode

Fig. 2. Typical cyclic voltammogram of chloramphenicol palmitate in pH 10.0; concn.=0.5 mM, scan rate= 40 mV s^{-1} .

of area 0.0223 cm^2 were employed as working electrodes and a $\text{Ag}/\text{AgCl(s), Cl}^-$ electrode was used as reference electrode. Platinum wire was used as the auxiliary electrode. A glassy carbon ring disk electrode was used as the working electrode. The pH measurements were carried out with an Elico digital pH meter. All experiments were carried out at $28 \pm 1^\circ$.

Fig. 3. Typical differential pulse polarogram of chloramphenicol palmitate in pH 10.0; concn.=0.5 mM, drop time=2 s.

The stock solution of the drug was prepared in dimethyl formamide. The supporting electrolytes ranging from pH 2.0 to 12.0 were prepared by using 0.2 M boric acid, 0.05 M citric acid and 0.1 M tri-sodium orthophosphate. The test solution were prepared by dissolving the required quantity of the stock solution and making up with the supporting electrolyte to the required volume to get the desired concentration and deaerated with oxygen-free nitrogen gas. Triton X-100 (0.002%) was used as maximum suppressor whenever necessary.

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